

THE USE OF LOCAL COMPUTER NETWORKS IN IMPROVING THE
EFFICIENCY OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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***Anotatsiya.** Mazkur maqolada zamonaviy ta'limda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, lokal kompyuter tarmoqlaridan foydalanishning pedagogik va texnik jihatlari yoritilgan. Lokal tarmoqlar orqali tezkor axborot almashuvi, resurslardan samarali foydalanish hamda o'quvchilarning mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari asoslab berilgan. Maqoladagi fikrlarda lokal kompyuter tarmoqlaridan samarali foydalanish o'qitish sifatini oshirish va boshqaruvni takomillashtirishga xizmat qilishini ko'rsatadi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, lokal kompyuter tarmog'i, tarmoq topologiyasi, server–mijoz arxitekturasi, ta'lim jarayoni, test nazorati.*

***Annotation.** This article discusses the pedagogical and technical aspects of using information and communication technologies and local computer networks in modern education. The possibilities of fast information exchange through local networks, efficient use of resources, and the development of students' independent working skills are substantiated. The study shows that effective use of local computer networks improves the quality of teaching and enhances management efficiency.*

***Keywords:** information and communication technologies, local computer network, network topology, client–server architecture, educational process, test control.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматриваются педагогические и технические аспекты использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий и локальных компьютерных сетей в современном образовании. Обоснованы возможности быстрого обмена информацией, эффективного использования ресурсов, а также формирования у обучающихся навыков самостоятельной работы. Результаты исследования показывают, что эффективное использование локальных компьютерных сетей способствует повышению качества обучения и совершенствованию управления.*

***Ключевые слова:** информационно-коммуникационные технологии, локальная*

компьютерная сеть, топология сети, клиент-серверная архитектура, образовательный процесс, тестовый контроль.

In the modern education system, the role of information and communication technologies (ICT) is invaluable. In particular, the effective use of local computer networks in educational buildings, information resource centers, and computer laboratories contributes to improving the quality of education and the efficiency of management. Local computer networks serve as an important tool in providing information support for the educational process, monitoring, assessing knowledge, and improving interaction between teachers and students. The connection features of local networks play a significant role in enabling students to work effectively during training sessions. Computer network topology (layout, structure, and composition) refers to the relative placement of computers in a network and the methods of connecting communication channels. The concept of topology primarily applies to local networks, as their communication structure can be easily observed. In global networks, however, the structure of communication is hidden from users and is not critically important, since each connection can be established through its own independent path.

Network topology determines the requirements for network devices, the type of cable used, the possible methods of data exchange, the most convenient management approach, reliability, and network scalability. Although users may not always have the opportunity to choose a network topology, understanding the characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages of basic topologies is essential. In educational institutions, three types of local network topologies are commonly used. The “Bus” topology connects all computers in parallel to a single communication line, where information transmitted from one computer is simultaneously received by all others. Centralized control can be implemented in a bus topology, where one client computer (the “central” unit) sends requests to all other objects to determine which one wishes to transmit data. After granting permission, the object transmits data and notifies the central unit upon completion. During signal transmission along the bus topology cable, signal attenuation occurs and is not restored, which limits the total cable length. Additionally, client computers receive signals of varying amplitudes depending on the distance between transmitting and receiving devices, increasing the requirements for network reception equipment. To extend the network length, multiple segments connected by repeaters are often used; however, the

network length cannot be increased indefinitely due to physical signal propagation limits. The management advantages and disadvantages of this topology are similar to those of the star topology, with the difference that in this case, the central unit does not transmit data between objects but only controls data exchange. In many cases, distributed random access control is used in bus topology networks, where all devices have equal access rights. Decisions about packet transmission are made locally by each device after analyzing network conditions, which may lead to competition, collisions, and data transmission errors.

In the “Star” topology, all computers are connected to a single central computer using separate communication channels. This topology has a clearly defined center, through which all data exchange occurs, resulting in a high workload on the central computer. Client computers do not have equal rights, and the central computer is typically more powerful. Due to centralized control, no conflicts occur in star topology networks. In terms of reliability, failure of one client computer does not affect others; however, failure of the central computer disables the entire network. Cable damage affects only the connected computer. A major limitation of the star topology is the limited number of client computers it can support, typically 8–16. Star topology is divided into “Active Star” and “Passive Star” configurations. In practice, the passive star topology is more widespread, including in the Internet, where hubs or concentrators are used instead of central computers to regenerate and distribute signals. The primary advantage of the star topology is the centralization of all connection points, which simplifies network monitoring, fault isolation, and access control. The “Ring” topology connects each computer to exactly two others, forming a closed loop. Each computer receives data from one neighbor and transmits it to the next. In this topology, each computer regenerates the signal, eliminating signal attenuation across the entire network. However, failure of a controlling node can halt all communication. The main advantage of the ring topology is the ability to significantly increase network length through signal regeneration. In some cases, other topologies such as the “Tree” topology are also used in educational environments. The tree topology consists of multiple star topologies combined and may be active (with central computers) or passive (with hubs). Currently, the process of informatization of the education system through modern information technologies, computerization, and networking is rapidly developing in the country. The National Program for Personnel Training emphasizes the development of modern information technologies and the

enhancement of educational processes using computer networks. One of the most important challenges in education is evaluating the effectiveness of teaching methods, particularly assessment methods. Various qualitative and quantitative indicators are used to assess students' knowledge, skills, and competencies, including differentiation, memorization, independent activity, and transfer of knowledge. During instruction, attention is given to students' ability to work independently using personal computers. Properly organized assessment fosters responsibility, discipline, activity, persistence, independence, goal orientation, and organization among students. According to the pedagogical scholar V.P. Bepalko, knowledge assessment includes four indicators: recognition, reproduction, transformation, and creative application of acquired information.

In teaching the subject "Information Technologies," extensive use is made of personal computers. Without network connectivity, however, their full potential cannot be utilized. Local networks allow efficient data collection and centralized test administration. Test-based assessment implemented via local networks significantly improves educational quality by reducing time and labor costs. In networked computer classrooms, the teacher's workstation functions as a server, while students' computers act as clients. The server manages access to shared resources and distributes test materials, while restricting unauthorized modification of results. This approach ensures objective evaluation of students' knowledge. In a local network, one computer functions as a server, managing communication, access rights, and shared resources such as memory, printers, scanners, and storage devices. Data exchange speeds in local networks range from 10 to 100 megabits per second, enabling high-quality information transmission. During lessons, teachers distribute tasks from the server to client workstations and monitor students' progress in real time. Tasks may be assigned individually, ensuring personalized learning.

In conclusion, the use of local computer networks in educational institutions increases the effectiveness of the learning process, improves assessment systems, and accelerates information exchange. Proper selection of network topology ensures technical stability, security, and cost efficiency. Rational use of local and global networks is a key factor in training competitive, knowledgeable, and independent-thinking professionals.

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